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#STI22GRX

Do Women Undertake Interdisciplinary Research More Than Men? ¹

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Introduction

Evidence suggests that junior women scientists are sometimes discouraged from pursuing interdisciplinary research (Smith-Doerr & Croissant, 2016). While interdisciplinary research does carry some risk, particularly to scientists in their early career stages, collaborative research efforts generally, as well as interdisciplinarity, may benefit the citation impact of the resulting publications (Freeman & Huang, 2014). If women, relative to men, are more likely to perceive interdisciplinary work as too high-risk, and if funders do not take action to correct the potential consequences of such perceptions, the overall research ecosystem could be negatively impacted. For instance, women could end up with a lower propensity toward interdisciplinary research than men.

To assess the current situation, survey and bibliometric data can be used to compare the interdisciplinarity of men and women researchers. In both a survey by Rhoten & Pfirman (2007) and a large-scale bibliometric analysis in support of a recent evaluation of the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada’s Discovery Research Program (Science-Metrix, 2019), women were not found to be less interdisciplinary than men. Using publication data for roughly 10,000 NSERC awardees, the latter study showed that female researchers actually exhibited higher rates of highly interdisciplinary papers (those in the top 10%) than male researchers (11% vs. 9.2%).

This latter result, because it is contrary to the outcome expected from women being discouraged from taking part in interdisciplinary work, raised concerns that a measurement bias owing to women self-citing less than men (Andersen, Schneider, Jagsi, & Nielsen, 2019) could have been at play. Indeed, interdisciplinarity was, as is often the case, inferred by the disciplinary diversity of the cited references of publications (Porter & Rafols, 2009). Accordingly, it is possible that a greater share of self-citations could decrease a paper’s interdisciplinarity by concentrating references in the core disciplines of the authors, leading to a reduced balance of represented disciplines and the average distance between them. Testing if such a measurement bias is at play is important as the bias could lead to erroneous conclusions regarding gender-based differences in the interdisciplinarity of research. If such a bias was present, one could find, after correcting for self-citations, that women do not differ from men in their propensity to perform interdisciplinary research or, perhaps, that they even participate less than men in such

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endeavors. Accordingly, it is important to assess and resolve this potential bias prior to drawing any conclusions from potential interdisciplinary differences between genders.

The goal of this study was thus to investigate the magnitude and direction of the relationship between the gender composition of a paper's co-authors and its interdisciplinarity, accounting for a potential measurement bias mediated by self-citations, among several other factors (e.g., number of authors, seniority and prior publication output).

Methods

Dataset

In this study, we made use of Scopus data for the 10-year period between 2010 and 2019. We considered only peer-reviewed publications (journal articles, reviews, and conference papers) classified across 174 mutually exclusive subfields as defined under Science-Metrix's journal-based classification of science (Rivest, Vignola-Gagné, & Archambault, 2021). This is the classification used throughout this paper in computing the interdisciplinarity scores of individual papers as well as in normalizing indicators. As this work was performed as part of a project for the European Commission, the analysis was further limited to papers where at least one author from a European Research Area (ERA) country was identified, for reasons detailed below. In total, roughly 9 million documents were analyzed, with approximately 7.5 million distinct authors.

Scopus includes an author identifier number (the AUID), which aims to aggregate each individual author's publications. This helps to identify self-citations, among other things, as the AUID identifies an author's full set of papers (removing false positives due to homonyms) even when there may be variations in the spelling or initialization of names. An assessment of the AUID showed that it produced reliable conclusions in a North American/European context when at least 1,000 authors were available per comparison group (Campbell & Struck, 2019). In a test set of 10,000 authors, their study also showed that the average recall and precision per author were, respectively, 98% and 96.9%; as the current study relies on millions of authors, we are confident the use of AUIDs is offering robust results for gender inference and the identification of self-citations.

Gender

We genderized the author names in Scopus using the NamSor API. As author names within an AUID may vary due to differences in spelling, typographical errors, or the presence of full name versus initials only (for which gender cannot usually be assigned), a method was devised to aggregate the predicted gender of the name variants of an AUID. For each name variant, the API generated a probability of the name being that of a man or woman. First, the average probability for each gender across name variants was computed for each AUID. Where this average for one gender exceeded 80%, the AUID was assigned to this gender. Second, if a name variant's probability exceeded 80% for one gender and the average of probabilities for that gender was between 65% and 80%, a gender was attributed. AUIDs that were assigned to multiple genders using this criterion (<0.05%), or for which a gender could not be attributed at all, were treated as unassigned. Across ERA countries for the period 2010–2019, approximately 18.9% of AUIDs were not assigned by the API using this gender assignment rule (GA #1).

Further GA rules were used to test the robustness of the findings obtained with different percentages of authors with an unassigned gender and different reliability levels of the assignment:

To further test the robustness of the findings to variation in the percentages of authors with an unassigned gender, and in the reliability of the assignment, results were produced using two additional GA rules:

- Relaxed rule (GA #2): A gender was assigned to an author if the average probability for one gender across the name variants exceeded 50%. This led to a reduction in the share of authors with an unassigned gender from 18.9% with GA #1 to 9.0%.
- Stringent rule (GA #3): A gender was assigned to an author if the average probability for one gender across the name variants exceeded 90% OR if at least one of the name variants scored a probability for one gender exceeding 90%, with the average across the name variants for the corresponding gender being between 75% and 90%. This led to an increase in the share of authors with an unassigned gender from 18.9% with GA #1 to 27.4%.

Interdisciplinarity

Following the work of Porter and Rafols (2009), interdisciplinarity was investigated using the Rao-Stirling index (RS) to quantify the diversity of integrated knowledge as represented in a publication's references. Each paper was assigned an interdisciplinarity score from 0 (i.e., completely following predominant citation patterns) to 1, the latter being extremely interdisciplinary (i.e., diverging completely from normal citation patterns in Scopus, integrating knowledge from areas that others do not), using the following formula:

$$RS = 1 - \sum_{i,j} s_{ij}p_i p_j = \sum_{i,j} d_{ij}p_i p_j$$

Where p_i and p_j are the respective proportions of references in subfields i and j in a paper's reference list (whereby $p_i p_j$ captures the variety and balance of represented subfields). The summation is taken over all cells of the subfield-by-subfield similarity matrix, accounting for all subfields in the Science-Matrix classification. s_{ij} is the cosine similarity between subfields i and j and captures how close (or distant, by taking $d_{ij} = 1 - s_{ij}$ as in the above formula for interdisciplinarity) the integrated subfields are in a given paper; the cosine similarity matrix between subfields is computed relying on the subfield co-citation network in a reference set of papers (here the whole of Scopus).

In this paper, we converted interdisciplinarity scores into a binary variable identifying highly interdisciplinary publications (i.e., the top 10%) by subfield, year and document type. Papers tied at the passing threshold for the top 10% were included in the group of highly interdisciplinary papers. The binary variable for interdisciplinarity that was later used in modelling the relationship between gender and interdisciplinarity was computed in two different ways: once considering all references made by papers in the database, and once where paper-to-paper self-citations were excluded. Paper-to-paper self-citations are those instances where at least one of the citing paper's AUIDs also appeared among the AUIDs of the cited papers. Note that self-citations were not removed in computing the subfields' proximity matrix to ensure comparability in the scores computed with and without self-citations at the paper level. The interdisciplinarity score was only computed for papers with at least five references with a known subfield after removal of self-citations. The regression models presented below were only estimated using papers (~6.8 million) for which a gender was assigned to at least one author and for which interdisciplinarity scores were computed.

Multivariate modelling

Groups of papers binned by number of authors: To further investigate the magnitude and direction of the relationship between the presence of women authors on a paper and its interdisciplinarity, multivariate analysis was performed using the R package “fixest” (Berge, 2018). Different models accounted for groups of papers defined per their number of authors (i.e., 1, 2, 3 to 5, 6 to 10, or 11 to 20 authors), which enabled a better specification of the gender variables included in the regression models (see Table 1). The approach of grouping papers by number of authors also enabled us to test for the presence and magnitude of the relationship between women authors and interdisciplinarity across papers with different numbers of authors. For example, gender differences could have been observed among single-author papers but not among those with many authors.

Table 1. Variables used in the various groups (by number of authors) of regression models.

No. of authors	Variables for gender	Fixed effects	Control variables
1	Dummy variables: Female author; Unknown gender.	Fixed-effects for subfield and year of publication	- Number of authors (for groups with 3 to 5 or more authors) Only included in MS2:
2	Dummy variables: All female; Mixed genders; Unknown genders (if the gender of any author was unknown).		- Number of references (complemented by squared and cubic terms) - Number of self-citations
3 to 5	Dummy variables: One for each number of female authors in the paper (1 to 5 female authors).		- Number of previous papers: count of papers previously published by any co-author of a given paper. In the models with only 2 authors, the <u>max.</u> and the min. number of previous papers (across co-authors) was used, since it provided the number of papers of each co-author. For the papers with more authors, having the min. and the max. number of papers would not capture all the previous output from the co-authors, so we used the total number of previous papers by the team. For single-author papers, these options would be equivalent.
6 to 10 and 10 to 20	Number of female authors; Number of unknown authors.		- Max. seniority: highest number of years since first publication in Scopus among a paper's co-authors - Min. seniority: smallest number of years since first publication in Scopus among a paper's co-authors

Two model specifications per group of regressions: At first, the regression models were estimated using a simple model specification (MS1) including gender as a predictor of interdisciplinarity, the number of authors (for groups of regressions using papers with 3 or more authors) as a control variable, and subfield and year fixed-effects.

Including the number of authors as a control variable is important as it may confound the effect of gender, expressed as the number of women authors, on interdisciplinarity. The number of authors influences the number of women authors, and larger teams are, to some degree, more likely than smaller ones to cross several disciplinary boundaries.

The subfield and year fixed-effects are also important as they mitigate the potential influence of subfields and years on the observed results. In the case of subfields, the fixed-effects control for differences in citation practices and database coverage across subfields that impact interdisciplinary measurements. At the same time, they eliminate an effect of women that would be mediated by gender differences in subfield preferences. This model specification was taken as our baseline for measuring the total effect of women on interdisciplinarity, disregarding differences owing to subfield/year of activity.

Subsequently, a second set of models (MS2) were estimated, adding further control variables to MS1. These were intended to control for other factors that could be partly mediating an effect of women authors on interdisciplinarity. Of particular relevance was a paper's number of author self-citations, which was used to assess whether part of the total effect of gender on interdisciplinarity may be mediated through a measurement bias. To properly assess the strength and direction of a potential bias introduced by self-citations, other controls included the number of prior publications by a paper's authors (measuring how prolific they are), their seniority (as a team), as well as the paper's number of listed references. Author characteristics were obtained via the Scopus AUIDs. See Table 1 for more details on the definition of these control variables for the various groups of regressions based on number of authors.

Results

Tables 2 to 6 provide detailed results of the logistic regressions estimated for the various groups of papers binned based on their number of authors. For the two groups of papers with more than 6 authors (6 to 10, and 11 to 20 authors), all models included an interaction term between the number of female authors and the number of authors because the effect of the former variable may be higher in smaller teams. Additionally, they included quadratic terms for the number of female authors alone and interacted with the total number of authors. This to account for possible non-linear effects whereby the first woman added to a research team might have a larger impact on interdisciplinarity than the 10th woman added to a team. The coefficients for these three terms are omitted in Table 5 and Table 6 as their effect was integrated into the reported coefficient for the number of female authors and the number of authors. Also note that in these tables, the effect of each additional woman author is conditional on the number of women already figuring in a research team and on the size of the team. Accordingly, the reported odds ratios in Table 5 (6–10 authors) are for 7-author papers (the average in this group being 7.3) with 2 women already figuring in the team (the average being 2.13). In Table 6 (11–20 authors), they are for 13-author papers (the average being 13.4) with 4 women already in the team (the average being 4.11).

The presence of women on papers was associated with a higher probability of papers figuring among the most interdisciplinary in their subfield and year for the groups of papers involving up to 10 authors, with or without controlling for a potential bias due to self-citations. For these 4 groups of papers (i.e., 1, 2, 3 to 5, or 6 to 10 authors), the measured effects of gender on interdisciplinarity were robust to changes in the model specification as well as in the gender assignment rule (Tables 2 to 5). The only exception related to the coefficients (or odds ratios) not being statistically significant, although still positive, for two out of five gender variables in the third group of regressions for publications with 3 to 5 co-authors, and only in the following cases (Table 4):

- the variable 5 female authors with both the moderate and relaxed (less precise) gender assignment rule (i.e., GA #1 and #2), and
- the variable 4 female authors using MS2 with the relaxed (less precise) gender assignment rule (GA #2).

In nearly all groups of regressions using MS2 (except papers with 11 to 20 authors), self-citations had a slightly negative, yet statistically significant effect on interdisciplinarity. The effect of self-citations is robust to changes in the model specification and the gender assignment rule. It is also worth noting that the negative effect of self-citations on interdisciplinarity is systematically reduced, and sometimes even cancelled, when interdisciplinarity is measured excluding self-citations (data not shown). This would partly explain why the effect size for gender (defined based on the presence and number of women authors on a publication) is systematically smaller under MS2 compared to MS1; in other words, part of the gender effect mediated through self-citations would be absorbed by the inclusion of self-citations in MS2.

Table 2. Logistic regression models for highly interdisciplinary papers (single-author papers).

Dependent variable: highly interdisciplinary publication (among 10% most interdisciplinary in the subfield and year of publication)

	Gender Assignment (GA) #1		GA #2	GA #3
	MS1	MS2	MS2	MS2
Female author	1.125*** [1.062; 1.192]	1.064* [1.005; 1.126]	1.062* [1.006; 1.122]	1.060* [1.000; 1.123]
Unknown gender	0.983 [0.923; 1.046]	0.928* [0.868; 0.993]	0.797** [0.677; 0.939]	0.982 [0.935; 1.032]
N references		1.001* [1.000; 1.002]	1.001* [1.000; 1.002]	1.001* [1.000; 1.002]
N self-citations		0.983*** [0.975; 0.991]	0.983*** [0.975; 0.991]	0.983*** [0.975; 0.991]
N previous papers		0.998*** [0.997; 0.999]	0.998*** [0.997; 0.999]	0.998*** [0.997; 0.999]
Seniority		0.994* [0.988; 0.999]	0.994* [0.988; 0.999]	0.994* [0.989; 0.999]
Fixed-Effects:				
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
subfield	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
S.E. type	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield
Observations	562,876	559,361	559,361	559,361
Squared Cor.	0.01233	0.01463	0.01468	0.01457
Pseudo R2	0.0171	0.01999	0.02004	0.01993
BIC	373,346	369,418	369,402	369,441

Note: The coefficients reported in this table refer to the odds-ratios. 95% confidence intervals are reported in brackets.

Significance levels: ' p < 0.1; * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001

Table 3. Logistic regression models for highly interdisciplinary papers (publications having only 2 authors).

Dependent variable: highly interdisciplinary publication (among 10% most interdisciplinary in the subfield and year of publication)

	Gender Assignment (GA) #1		GA #2	GA #3
	MS1	MS2	MS2	MS2
All female	1.238*** [1.127; 1.359]	1.144** [1.048; 1.248]	1.141** [1.048; 1.242]	1.143** [1.049; 1.247]
Mixed genders	1.134*** [1.074; 1.197]	1.103*** [1.048; 1.162]	1.010*** [1.047; 1.155]	1.102*** [1.044; 1.164]
Unknown genders	1.038' [0.997; 1.080]	1.000 [0.962; 1.038]	0.939 [0.867; 1.017]	1.023 [0.989; 1.058]
N references		0.999 [0.997; 1.001]	0.999 [0.997; 1.001]	0.999 [0.998; 1.001]
N self-citations		0.986** [0.978; 0.995]	0.986** [0.978; 0.995]	0.986** [0.978; 0.995]
Max. previous papers		0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]	0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]	0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]
Min. previous papers		0.999* [0.998; 1.000]	0.999* [0.998; 1.000]	0.999* [0.998; 1.000]
Max. seniority		0.984*** [0.980; 0.987]	0.984*** [0.980; 0.987]	0.984*** [0.980; 0.987]
Min. seniority		0.999 [0.995; 1.003]	0.999 [0.995; 1.003]	0.999 [0.995; 1.003]
Fixed-Effects:				
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
subfield	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
S.E. type	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield
Observations	1,067,909	1,060,901	1,060,901	1,060,901
Squared Cor.	0.005	0.008	0.008	0.008
Pseudo R2	0.008	0.011	0.011	0.011
BIC	695,421	688,114	688,092	688,159

Note: Same as previous table

Table 4. Logistic regression models for highly interdisciplinary papers (publications having 3 to 5 authors).

Dependent variable: highly interdisciplinary publication (among 10% most interdisciplinary in the subfield and year of publication)

	Gender Assignment (GA) #1		GA #2	GA #3
	MS1	MS2	MS2	MS2
4 authors	1.019 [0.9856; 1.0534]	1.071*** [1.0391; 1.1034]	1.069*** [1.0377; 1.1011]	1.072*** [1.0403; 1.1047]
5 authors	1.01 [0.9516; 1.0728]	1.114*** [1.0541; 1.1778]	1.110*** [1.0512; 1.1726]	1.116*** [1.0552; 1.1797]
1 female author	1.119*** [1.0642; 1.1775]	1.100*** [1.0482; 1.1544]	1.082*** [1.0388; 1.1264]	1.098*** [1.0445; 1.1531]
2 female authors	1.206*** [1.1032; 1.3173]	1.157*** [1.0641; 1.2578]	1.142*** [1.0594; 1.2314]	1.150** [1.0566; 1.2513]
3 female authors	1.238*** [1.1042; 1.3886]	1.155** [1.0375; 1.2858]	1.140* [1.0301; 1.2621]	1.154* [1.0335; 1.2884]
4 female authors	1.244** [1.0707; 1.4457]	1.131' [0.9834; 1.3012]	1.113 [0.9765; 1.2697]	1.139' [0.9903; 1.3092]
5 female authors	1.284** [1.0890; 1.5128]	1.132 [0.9692; 1.3216]	1.108 [0.9534; 1.2888]	1.154' [0.9759; 1.3654]
1 unknown gender	0.977' [0.9543; 1.0009]	0.967** [0.9448; 0.9895]	0.96 [0.9136; 1.0094]	0.979* [0.9606; 0.9982]
2 unknown genders	0.958' [0.916; 1.001]	0.917*** [0.881; 0.955]	0.917* [0.853; 0.986]	0.954** [0.923; 0.986]
3 unknown genders	0.943' [0.882; 1.007]	0.859*** [0.812; 0.908]	0.728*** [0.653; 0.811]	0.906*** [0.871; 0.942]
4 unknown genders	1.044 [0.926; 1.177]	0.892' [0.794; 1.002]	0.723** [0.578; 0.905]	0.896** [0.833; 0.964]
5 unknown genders	0.873 [0.683; 1.115]	0.677*** [0.543; 0.845]	0.819 [0.539; 1.245]	0.889' [0.789; 1.001]
N references		1.000 [0.998; 1.001]	0.999 [0.998; 1.001]	0.999 [0.998; 1.001]
N self-citations		0.982*** [0.977; 0.988]	0.983*** [0.977; 0.988]	0.982*** [0.977; 0.988]
N previous papers		0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]	0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]	0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]
Max. seniority		0.981*** [0.976; 0.986]	0.981*** [0.977; 0.986]	0.981*** [0.976; 0.986]
Min. seniority		0.996** [0.992; 0.999]	0.996* [0.993; 0.999]	0.996** [0.992; 0.999]
Fixed-Effects:				
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
subfield	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
S.E. type	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield
Observations	3,281,609	3,259,248	3,259,248	3,259,248
Squared Cor.	0.002	0.005	0.005	0.005
Pseudo R2	0.003	0.007	0.007	0.007
BIC	2,222,909	2,198,571	2,198,963	2,198,662

Note: Same as previous table

Table 5. Logistic regression models for highly interdisciplinary papers (publications having 6 to 10 authors).

Dependent variable: highly interdisciplinary publication (among 10% most interdisciplinary in the subfield and year of publication)

	Gender Assignment (GA) #1		GA #2	GA #3
	MS1	MS2	MS2	MS2
N authors (total)	0.957*** [0.938; 0.977]	0.994 [0.973; 1.016]	0.9941 [0.973; 1.015]	0.994 [0.972; 1.017]
N female authors	1.077*** [1.032; 1.123]	1.061** [1.019; 1.104]	1.0551** [1.016; 1.095]	1.056** [1.015; 1.097]
N unknown gender	0.980* [0.963; 0.998]	0.962*** [0.944; 0.979]	0.9852 [0.958; 1.014]	0.974*** [0.959; 0.988]
N references		1.000 [0.999; 1.002]	1.000 [0.998; 1.001]	1.000 [0.999; 1.002]
N self-citations		0.994* [0.988; 1.000]	0.9944* [0.989; 1.000]	0.994* [0.988; 0.999]
N previous papers		0.999*** [0.999; 1.000]	0.9995*** [0.9993; 0.9997]	0.9995*** [0.9993; 0.9997]
Max. seniority		0.979*** [0.971; 0.987]	0.9815*** [0.974; 0.989]	0.979*** [0.971; 0.987]
Min. seniority		0.991*** [0.986; 0.995]	0.9925** [0.988; 0.997]	0.991*** [0.986; 0.995]
Fixed-Effects:				
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
subfield	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
S.E. type	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield
Observations	1,850,767	1,840,752	1,840,752	1,840,752
Squared Cor.	0.006	0.009	0.008	0.009
Pseudo R2	0.008	0.012	0.012	0.012
BIC	1,214,649	1,204,412	1,205,039	1,204,500

Note: Same as previous table

Table 6. Logistic regression models for highly interdisciplinary papers (publications having 11 to 20 authors).

Dependent variable: highly interdisciplinary publication (among 10% most interdisciplinary in the subfield and year of publication)

	Gender Assignment (GA) #1		GA #2	GA #3
	MS1	MS2	MS2	MS2
N authors (total)	0.951*** [0.936; 0.967]	0.982* [0.965; 0.998]	0.981* [0.963; 0.998]	0.983' [0.967; 1.000]
N female authors	1.055* [1.010; 1.102]	1.035' [0.994; 1.078]	1.035' [0.994; 1.078]	1.03 [0.992; 1.068]
N unknown gender	0.993 [0.965; 1.021]	0.972* [0.945; 0.999]	0.981 [0.915; 1.051]	0.978* [0.959; 0.998]
N references		1.001 [1.000; 1.003]	1.001 [1.000; 1.003]	1.002' [1.000; 1.003]
N self-citations		0.999 [0.993; 1.005]	0.999 [0.993; 1.005]	0.999 [0.993; 1.005]
N previous papers		0.9996*** [0.9995; 0.9997]	0.9996*** [0.9995; 0.9997]	0.9996*** [0.9995; 0.9997]
Max. seniority		0.961*** [0.947; 0.975]	0.969*** [0.955; 0.983]	0.961*** [0.947; 0.975]
Min. seniority		0.978*** [0.968; 0.985]	0.979*** [0.970; 0.989]	0.976*** [0.968; 0.985]
Fixed-Effects:				
year	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
subfield	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
S.E. type	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield	year/subfield
Observations	408,544	407,319	407,319	407,319
Squared Cor.	0.017	0.020	0.019	0.020
Pseudo R2	0.026	0.031	0.030	0.031
BIC	214,347	212,669	212,802	212,670

Note: Same as previous table

Discussion

In a context where funding for interdisciplinary research is gaining in importance to help solve the increasingly complex problems faced by modern societies (such as those being addressed through the UN SDGs), obtaining accurate measurements of interdisciplinarity by gender is highly relevant for funders in taking appropriate action(s) to level the playing field across genders. This is even more relevant given the conflicting evidence (Leahey et al., 2017; Rhoten & Pfirman, 2007; Science-Metrix, 2019) concerning the presence of women in interdisciplinary research, some of which could be biased by self-citations and other factors.

The key result of this study is that the presence of women in scientific publications, within the large-scale dataset under investigation, is positively associated with interdisciplinarity even after controlling for a potential self-citation bias (shown to exert a slight negative effect on interdisciplinarity). This contradicts some of the prior literature on the topic (Leahey et al., 2017) but confirms results from other studies making use of different approaches—for example, using survey data (Rhoten & Pfirman, 2007). These results add to the body of literature that may suggest research performing and funding organizations should not be too concerned by women being potentially discouraged from taking part in interdisciplinary work. Nevertheless, further research would be warranted to better understand the potential impact of observed

gender differences in interdisciplinarity on, for example, career progression. For instance, prior work has suggested that current evaluation practices underlying tenure decision may not be properly accounting for the specificities of interdisciplinary work (Gewin, 2014). Also, further studies relying on alternative sources of information to capture interdisciplinarity (e.g., semantic analysis of full texts) could be useful to further test the robustness of this study's results.

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